

THE ADVANTAGES OF DIGITALIZATION OF TYPES OF PRACTICAL TASKS IN TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article explains the types of practical tasks in teaching technology subjects to students in an interesting and high-quality way, and their effective use in digitalization. It also highlights the importance of developing the skills and competencies of students in completing practical tasks in order to improve their creative abilities in technology, their ability to acquire a profession, new ideas, logical thinking, and the ability to perform independent work.

As a result of the increasing demands on theoretical knowledge and practical skills, qualifications, and competencies of individuals around the world, a wide range of scientific research is being conducted, making effective use of processes related to modern educational technologies. In particular, in our country, as in many developed countries, educational technologies are being effectively used at all stages of education to strengthen the professional training of young people studying there. Modern methods of education and upbringing study the tasks of forming students' worldviews, cultivating independence, initiative and abilities. Consideration of such important issues serves to ensure the unity of education and upbringing and the consolidation of students' knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Today, in our country, while further improving the education system, a number of mechanisms are being developed to conduct classes in accordance with modern standards. One of the main goals is for teachers to effectively use the conditions created in educational institutions to conduct quality classes. In technological education classes of higher educational institutions, it is necessary for students to use educational technology bases purposefully and effectively. Subject teachers play an important role in preparing students to correctly learn the words on the topics given in the curriculum of technological subjects. For this, it is necessary to select educational tools, visual aids, and tasks that are appropriate to the topic in order to organize the lesson in an interesting and high-quality way.

Research into the psychological foundations of the learning process and the formation of creative abilities of students formed the basis of a number of pedagogical theories. The gradual implementation of the formation of mental actions was highlighted by N.F. Talizina;

developmental education by V.V. Davidov; theories on the formation of the teacher's personality and his innovative activity were highlighted by V.A. Salstenin, L.S. Podimova. Consideration of such important issues serves to ensure the unity of education and the consolidation of students' knowledge, skills and qualifications.

In teaching technology to 9th grade students of secondary schools, a total of 34 hours of teaching materials are provided according to the annual calendar in two areas: "Technology and Design" and "Service". This includes chapters on the technology of making national handicraft products, the basics of production and household science, the basics of electronics, technologies for preparing creative projects and guidance on choosing a profession. The topics in the textbook that correspond to the annual calendar plan are taught in groups of boys and girls, and are not divided. However, for 9th grade students, practical tasks are not given at all in the topics given in technology, and more theoretical knowledge is given for the lesson process and homework, and partly practical questions are given.

For 9th grade students in technology, the following practical assignments can be digitized:

1. Calculate the dimensions of women's trousers based on the sketch and draw a drawing!
2. Prepare the pattern of the trousers!
3. Place the pattern of the trousers on the fabric and cut it out!
4. Process and sew the parts of the trousers!
5. Iron and finish the trousers!
6. Present the finished trousers!
7. Draw a drawing of a pleated pillow!
8. Prepare and sew the shapes of the pleated pillow!
9. Cut the pleated pillow based on the size!
10. Process and sew the seams of the pleated pillow, etc.

In conclusion, in teaching students about technology in an interesting and high-quality way, it is important to systematically master knowledge through the types of practical tasks, their effective use, and the effective use of technology and equipment to solve various problems in everyday life. This helps to develop students' logical thinking, thinking, practical skills, quick decision-making, and collaborative work and innovative approaches. By effectively organizing the digitalization of practical task methods, science teachers can increase students' interest in technology through the use of artificial intelligence (AI), which will provide a solid foundation for training them for successful careers in the future..

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